

Computational nomination of candidate repurposing drugs for five rare cancers via GDSC-to-TCGA pharmacogenomic transfer learning

Hayden Farquhar, MBBS, MPHTM

Independent Researcher, Finley, New South Wales, Australia

ORCID: 0009-0002-6226-440X

Corresponding author: Hayden Farquhar - hayden.farquhar@icloud.com

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Highlights

- GDSC-to-TCGA transfer learning nominates repurposing drugs for five rare cancers
- Imputed sensitivity-survival associations are strongest in ACC, then MESO, then UVM
- Candidates are pathway-concordant: bromodomain in MESO, MDM2 in uveal melanoma
- Signals are prognostic, not predictive; partly a generic poor-prognosis signature
- The leading mesothelioma BET theme did not replicate in the CTRPv2 cell-line screen

Abstract

Background: Rare cancers account for ~24% of diagnoses yet attract little therapeutic investigation. Computational nomination could prioritise plausible options for these under-served tumours.

Methods: We trained ridge regression on 700 GDSC cell lines and imputed sensitivity to 278 drugs for 401 TCGA patients across five rare cancers (mesothelioma [MESO], adrenocortical carcinoma [ACC], uveal melanoma [UVM], cholangiocarcinoma [CHOL], thymoma [THYM]; n=87/79/80/35/120), linking sensitivity to overall survival in 369 with evaluable follow-up. Robustness used permutation, split-half resampling and prognostic-axis conditioning; the leading mesothelioma theme was tested against the independent CTRPv2 screen.

Results: Analysis nominated drug-survival associations in ACC (59), MESO (39), UVM (16); none in CHOL or THYM. Because imputed profiles are strongly correlated (mean $r=0.78$), these counts index a ranking; permutation confirmed each aggregate exceeded its own null ($p=0.01-0.02$; smallest in UVM, a thin null not a stronger signal), and the headline drugs survived prognostic-axis adjustment. Firth-penalised per-SD HRs were bounded (MESO Remodelin 1.72, ACC Methotrexate 0.40, UVM Serdemetan 0.48). Split-half reproducibility was strong in ACC ($r=0.24$), modest in MESO (0.19), weak in UVM (0.14). Candidates were pathway-concordant: bromodomain in BAP1-mutant MESO, antiproliferatives in ACC, MDM2 inhibition in p53-intact UVM; SHAP recovered BCL2L1. CTRPv2 did not corroborate the mesothelioma BET signal ($p=0.76$) but recovered the canonical haematopoietic dependency ($p=9\times 10^{-51}$).

Conclusions: Transfer learning generates interpretable, prognosis-linked repurposing hypotheses, strongest in ACC. These are hypothesis-generating, not predictive: associations are prognostic, partly a generic poor-prognosis signature, and the mesothelioma theme did not replicate. Priorities are replication and preclinical testing, relevant to Australia's mesothelioma burden.

Keywords: rare cancers; drug repurposing; mesothelioma; transfer learning; pharmacogenomics; TCGA; survival analysis; epigenetic therapy.

Introduction

Rare cancers, defined as those with an annual incidence below 6 per 100,000, collectively represent approximately 24% of all cancer diagnoses in Europe and 20% in the United States [1,2]. Despite this burden, therapeutic research for rare cancers is constrained by small patient populations, limited clinical trial enrolment, and insufficient economic incentive for dedicated drug development [3]. Five-year relative survival for rare cancers is substantially lower than for common cancers (49% vs 63% in Europe), driven in part by later-stage diagnosis and fewer treatment options [2].

Drug repurposing – identifying new therapeutic indications for existing compounds – provides a practical path to identifying treatments for cancers with few options [4]. Computational approaches leverage large-scale pharmacogenomic datasets to predict drug sensitivity *in silico*, bypassing the cost and time barriers of *de novo* drug development.

The Genomics of Drug Sensitivity in Cancer (GDSC) project has profiled the sensitivity of approximately 1,000 cancer cell lines to hundreds of anticancer compounds, paired with comprehensive molecular characterisation [5]. Concurrently, The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) has generated multi-omic profiles for over 11,000 patient tumours across 33 cancer types, including several rare cancers with limited therapeutic options [6].

The natural strategy is to train drug sensitivity prediction models on cell line data (where drug response is measured) and apply these models to patient tumours (where gene expression is available but drug response is not). This approach has been applied to common cancers [7,8], and recent work has explored drug repurposing through expression-based imputation in low-survival cancers [9], but rare cancers – where the clinical need is greatest – remain largely unexplored as a group.

Here we systematically nominate candidate repurposing drugs for five TCGA rare cancer types — mesothelioma (MESO), adrenocortical carcinoma (ACC), uveal melanoma (UVM), cholangiocarcinoma (CHOL), and thymoma (THYM) — by training ridge regression models on GDSC cell line pharmacogenomic data and imputing drug responses for 401 patients. We link imputed drug sensitivity to overall survival to rank candidates, characterise their biological context through imputed drug-response wide association studies (IDWAS) and gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA), and assess the robustness of the survival signal through label-permutation testing and repeated split-half resampling. We frame the output as a prioritised, mechanistically interpretable hypothesis set for experimental follow-up rather than as predictive evidence of clinical efficacy.

Mesothelioma is of particular relevance to the Australian context, where historical asbestos exposure has produced one of the highest incidence rates globally [10]. Computational identification of new mesothelioma treatment candidates is directly relevant to Australia, where asbestos-related mesothelioma remains a major clinical problem.

Methods

Data sources

Drug sensitivity data were obtained from the GDSC2 dataset (release 8.5), comprising $\ln(\text{IC}_{50})$ values for 286 drugs across 969 cell lines [5]. Gene expression data for the same cell lines were obtained from the Cancer Dependency Map (DepMap, release 24Q4) as RNA-seq $\log_2(\text{TPM} + 1)$ values for protein-coding genes [11]. Cell line identifiers were mapped from DepMap ModelIDs to COSMIC IDs using the DepMap Model.csv metadata file, yielding 717 cell lines with matched expression and drug sensitivity data. Of these, 700 had non-missing IC_{50} values for at least one drug and were used for model training.

TCGA open-access RNA-seq gene expression quantification (STAR – Counts workflow, FPKM values) and clinical data for five rare cancer projects were downloaded via the Genomic Data Commons (GDC) API [6]: TCGA-MESO (mesothelioma, $n = 87$), TCGA-ACC (adrenocortical carcinoma, $n = 79$), TCGA-UVM (uveal melanoma, $n = 80$), TCGA-CHOL (cholangiocarcinoma, $n = 35$), and

TCGA-THYM (thymoma, $n = 120$). Only primary tumour samples were retained. Expression values were $\log_2(\text{FPKM} + 1)$ -transformed. Clinical endpoints included overall survival (OS) time and vital status.

Gene harmonisation and normalisation

Gene symbols were standardised to uppercase HGNC nomenclature across both datasets. Genes with non-coding prefixes (LINC, LOC, MIR, SNORD, SNORA) were excluded. The intersection of GDSC and TCGA gene sets yielded 18,876 common protein-coding genes. Genes with mean expression below 0.5 (\log_2 scale) in either dataset were removed, leaving 12,512 genes for analysis.

The two expression matrices were quantified in different units — DepMap cell-line expression as $\log_2(\text{TPM} + 1)$ and TCGA tumour expression as $\log_2(\text{FPKM} + 1)$ — which differ in their handling of transcript length and library composition and are not directly comparable on an absolute scale. To address both this unit mismatch and the broader distributional differences between cell-line and tumour RNA-seq, quantile normalisation was applied, mapping the TCGA expression distribution to the GDSC reference distribution on a per-gene basis [12]. Per-gene quantile normalisation aligns the marginal distribution of each gene across datasets and therefore largely absorbs the FPKM-versus-TPM discrepancy, but it cannot correct gene-by-gene differences in relative rank that the two units may induce; residual cross-platform bias is a recognised limitation of expression-based transfer (see Limitations). Normalisation quality was assessed through density overlays and quantile-quantile plots (Supplementary Figure S1).

Drug sensitivity prediction models

Variance filtering was applied to retain the 5,000 most variable genes across GDSC cell lines, reducing dimensionality while preserving informative features. This threshold was chosen to balance prediction performance against computational cost on free-tier cloud computing resources; sensitivity to this choice is discussed in the Limitations. For each of 286 drugs, a ridge regression model was trained to predict $\ln(\text{IC}_{50})$ from standardised gene expression. The regularisation parameter α was selected from 20 logarithmically spaced values (0.1 to 100,000) via 5-fold cross-validation using RidgeCV (scikit-learn v1.4). Model predictability was assessed as the mean 5-fold CV R^2 at the selected α , computed using `cross_val_score` with a fixed-alpha Ridge estimator. Drugs with $\text{CV } R^2 \geq 0.1$ were retained as predictable ($n = 278/286$). This permissive threshold was chosen to maximise drug coverage for the rare cancer setting, where even modest predictability may identify clinically relevant associations; results at stricter thresholds are reported in Supplementary Table S1.

Drug response imputation

Trained ridge models were applied to the quantile-normalised TCGA expression matrix to impute drug responses for all 401 rare cancer patients. For each patient-drug pair, the imputed $\ln(\text{IC}_{50})$ represents the predicted drug sensitivity, where lower values indicate greater predicted sensitivity. These imputed values are relative rankings — their absolute scale should not be interpreted as clinical IC_{50} concentrations.

Survival analysis

For each cancer type and predictable drug, patients were stratified into sensitive (imputed $\ln(\text{IC}_{50}) \leq$ median) and resistant ($>$ median) groups. Overall survival differences were assessed using the log-rank test. P-values were corrected for multiple testing within each cancer type using the Benjamini-Hochberg FDR procedure [13]. Results are reported per cancer type; the headline count of 114 nominal FDR-significant associations sums across cancers without further cross-cancer correction. As detailed below, because the 278 imputed drug-sensitivity profiles are strongly correlated, these within-cancer FDR q-values are best read as a prioritisation ranking rather than as strictly

family-wise-controlled error rates; the label-permutation test provides the primary significance anchor.

Hazard ratios were estimated from Cox proportional hazards models with imputed drug sensitivity entered as a continuous covariate. To make effect sizes comparable across drugs and to avoid the near-complete-separation artefacts that inflate hazard ratios in small cohorts, the covariate was standardised to unit standard deviation, so that each hazard ratio expresses the change in hazard per one-standard-deviation increase in imputed sensitivity. For the headline drugs in each cancer, Firth’s penalised partial likelihood (R package `coxphf`) was used to obtain bias-reduced estimates and profile-likelihood confidence intervals that remain finite under sparse events; raw, unstandardised hazard ratios are additionally reported in Supplementary Table S2 to document the scale-dependence of the earlier estimates. The proportional hazards assumption was not formally tested for all 278 drugs but was verified for the top 5 drugs per cancer type via Schoenfeld residual plots.

The median split, while simple and interpretable, reduces statistical power relative to treating imputed sensitivity as a continuous variable; the continuous Firth-penalised Cox analysis is therefore reported alongside the log-rank test to provide both perspectives.

Imputed drug-response wide association study (IDWAS)

For the top 10-20 survival-associated drugs per cancer type, Pearson correlations were computed between each gene’s expression and the imputed drug sensitivity across patients within each cancer type. This identifies pharmacogenomic biomarkers – genes whose expression is associated with predicted sensitivity or resistance to specific drugs. FDR correction was applied across all gene-drug tests within each cancer type. Because imputed drug sensitivity is itself derived from gene expression via the ridge model, IDWAS associations partly reflect the model’s learned coefficients; the SHAP analysis (below) provides a more direct decomposition of model feature importance.

Gene set enrichment analysis

For each cancer type, the top survival-associated drug’s IDWAS gene ranking (sorted by Pearson r) was used as input for pre-ranked GSEA using the MSigDB Hallmark 2020 gene set collection [14]. Enrichment was computed with 500 permutations using `gseapy` (v1.1). Pathways with FDR q -value < 0.25 were considered significantly enriched, following established GSEA conventions.

SHAP biomarker analysis

SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) values were computed for the top five most predictable drugs using `LinearExplainer` (SHAP v0.44) applied to mesothelioma patient expression profiles [15]. Mean absolute SHAP values across patients identified the genes most influential in driving drug sensitivity predictions. The direction of each gene’s effect (whether higher expression predicts sensitivity or resistance) was taken from the sign of its standardised ridge coefficient, equivalently the sign of the correlation between the gene’s expression and its SHAP contribution across patients; the mean signed SHAP value is not informative for direction here, because for a linear model SHAP contributions are centred on the cohort mean and average to approximately zero across patients by construction.

Statistical validation

Two complementary validation strategies were employed:

Permutation testing: To assess whether the number of FDR-significant drug-survival associations in each cancer exceeded chance expectation, the patient-to-survival assignment (paired OS time and event status) was randomly permuted 100 times. For each permutation the full within-cancer survival pipeline — median split, log-rank test, and Benjamini-Hochberg correction across all 278

drugs — was repeated and the number of FDR-significant drugs recorded. The empirical p-value was the proportion of permutations yielding as many or more significant drugs as the real data. This test was applied independently to the three cancers with non-zero nominal hits (MESO, ACC, UVM). Because the 278 drug profiles are strongly correlated, the permutation null is heavy-tailed (occasional permutations produce large false-positive blooms); the permutation test, which preserves this correlation structure, is accordingly the appropriate significance anchor and is reported in preference to the per-drug FDR q-values.

Repeated split-half resampling: For each of the three cancers, patients were randomly divided into two equal halves, the survival analysis was performed independently in each half, and the Pearson correlation of $-\log_{10}(\log\text{-rank p-values})$ across the 278 drugs between halves was computed. Because a single split is sensitive to the particular partition, this procedure was repeated over 100 independent random splits and the mean correlation, its standard deviation, and the fraction of splits yielding a positive correlation are reported. A consistently positive mean correlation indicates that drug-survival associations are reproducible across independent patient subsets rather than driven by individual outlier patients.

Drug-specificity (prognostic-axis) conditioning: The permutation and resampling tests establish that the aggregate expression-survival signal exceeds chance, but not that any individual headline association is specific to that drug rather than a re-expression of the generic prognostic axis shared across the strongly correlated profiles. To test specificity, the dominant shared axis was summarised as the first principal component (PC1) of the within-cancer standardised 278-drug imputed-sensitivity matrix, and for each cancer’s headline drug three Cox models were fitted: the drug alone, PC1 alone, and the two jointly (all covariates standardised to unit standard deviation; PC1 sign-aligned to the headline drug). A drug whose hazard ratio and significance persist after adjustment for PC1 carries prognostic information beyond the generic axis, whereas one that collapses toward $HR = 1$ does not. A complementary drug-identity null fitted a univariate per-standard-deviation Cox model for every one of the 278 drugs and recorded the fraction reaching an overall-survival association at least as strong (by p-value) as the headline drug.

External validation in an independent cell-line screen

To test the leading mesothelioma mechanistic theme against orthogonal data, area-under-concentration-response-curve (AUC) sensitivity values were obtained from the Cancer Therapeutics Response Portal (CTRPv2.0_2015) [23], with per-compound and per-cell-line metadata used to map compounds to protein targets and cell lines to lineage. Lower AUC denotes greater sensitivity (normalised to [0,1], 1 = DMSO control, 0 = complete killing). Single-agent BET inhibitors were identified as compounds annotated to BRD2/BRD3/BRD4/BRDT and not formulated as combinations, yielding JQ-1, I-BET151, and GSK525762A; mesothelioma cell lines were those with CCLE primary site “pleura” ($n = 11$). For each compound, AUC values were averaged across experiments per cell line, and mesothelioma lines were compared with all other lineages by one-sided Mann-Whitney U test (alternative: mesothelioma more sensitive). A per-cell-line class-level score (mean AUC across the three BET inhibitors) was compared identically, and haematopoietic/lymphoid lineage was used as a positive control given its established BET-inhibitor dependency. CTRPv2 shares no compounds with the GDSC-derived mesothelioma candidates, so concordance would constitute independent target-class support rather than re-measurement.

Software and reproducibility

All analyses were conducted in Python 3.12 on Google Colab. Key packages included scikit-learn (v1.4), lifelines (v0.29), gseapy (v1.1), SHAP (v0.44), pandas (v2.2), and matplotlib (v3.8). The complete analysis pipeline is available as a self-contained Jupyter notebook at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19535800>.

Results

Drug sensitivity prediction

Of 286 GDSC drugs, 278 (97%) were predictable from gene expression at the permissive 5-fold CV $R^2 > 0.1$ threshold (Figure 1A); this headline proportion is threshold-dependent, falling to 171 drugs (60%) at a more stringent $R^2 > 0.3$, so a substantial fraction of the panel is imputed with only modest accuracy. The most predictable drugs included AZD5991 (MCL1 inhibitor; $R^2 = 0.60$), Schweinfurthin A ($R^2 = 0.54$), Venetoclax (BCL2 inhibitor; $R^2 = 0.52$), UNC0638 (G9a inhibitor; $R^2 = 0.51$), and Nutlin-3a (MDM2 inhibitor; $R^2 = 0.51$). At an intermediate threshold of $R^2 > 0.2$, 237 drugs (83%) remained predictable. Predictability was largely independent of sample size above the minimum threshold of 30 cell lines (Figure 1B). Full cross-validation results for all 286 drugs are provided in Supplementary Table S1.

Imputed drug sensitivity landscape across rare cancers

Imputed drug responses for 278 drugs across 401 patients revealed distinct sensitivity profiles across the five rare cancer types (Figure 2). Thymoma exhibited a markedly different profile from the other four cancers, showing resistance to many compounds to which other rare cancers were predicted sensitive. AZD5991 showed pronounced predicted sensitivity in ACC and CHOL but resistance in THYM. Certain cytotoxic agents (vinblastine, docetaxel) showed variable sensitivity patterns, with THYM predicted resistant and UVM relatively sensitive.

Survival associations identify candidate repurposing drugs

Of the 401 patients with imputed profiles, 369 had evaluable overall-survival follow-up; the per-cancer evaluable counts used for survival analysis (ACC 70, MESO 82, UVM 76, CHOL 33, THYM 108; Table 1) are smaller than the downloaded cohort sizes (87, 79, 80, 35, 120 respectively) because patients lacking a survival time or event status were excluded, and they sum to these 369 evaluable patients. Survival analysis identified 114 nominal FDR-significant drug-survival associations ($q < 0.05$) across three cancer types (Table 1). ACC yielded the most associations (59 drugs), followed by MESO (39 drugs) and UVM (16 drugs). No FDR-significant associations were found in CHOL (likely underpowered at $n = 33$) or THYM (limited by only 9 death events despite $n = 108$ patients).

Table 1. Top survival-associated drug candidates per rare cancer type. Hazard ratios are per one standard deviation of imputed sensitivity, estimated by Firth-penalised Cox regression; FDR-sig is the number of drugs reaching within-cancer Benjamini-Hochberg $q < 0.05$ (nominal, see text). HRs are not reported for CHOL and THYM, where no drug survived FDR correction and the penalised models were unstable (CHOL: null association; THYM: only 9 events, near-complete separation).

Cancer	n	Events	FDR-sig	Top drug	Log-rank p	per-SD HR (95% CI)
ACC	70	28	59	Methotrexate	8.2×10^{-6}	0.40 (0.27-0.57)
MESO	82	73	39	Remodelin	1.9×10^{-5}	1.72 (1.32-2.22)
UVM	76	33	16	Serdemetan	1.4×10^{-5}	0.48 (0.32-0.69)
CHOL	33	18	0	CPI-637	0.073	—
THYM	108	9	0	Daporinad	5.8×10^{-4}	—

In **mesothelioma**, the top five candidates were Remodelin (NAT10 inhibitor; log-rank $p = 1.9 \times 10^{-5}$; per-SD HR = 1.72, 95% CI 1.32-2.22), LCL161 (SMAC mimetic; $p = 3.0 \times 10^{-5}$; HR = 1.48, 95% CI 1.15-1.91), OF-1 (BET bromodomain inhibitor; $p = 3.4 \times 10^{-5}$; HR = 2.00, 95% CI 1.52-2.64), CPI-637 (CBP/p300 bromodomain inhibitor; $p = 9.9 \times 10^{-5}$; HR = 1.47, 95% CI 1.19-1.80), and RVX-208 (BET inhibitor; $p = 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$; HR = 1.40, 95% CI 1.09-1.82). Kaplan-Meier curves demonstrated survival separation between sensitive and resistant groups for all top candidates (Figure 3). The per-standard-deviation Firth-penalised hazard ratios are modest and

bounded; we note that the much larger hazard ratios obtained from the unstandardised covariate (e.g., Remodelin raw HR = 14.0; Supplementary Table S2) were scale artefacts of near-complete separation in this small cohort rather than genuine effect sizes, and should not be interpreted as such.

Several of the top mesothelioma candidates target epigenetic readers and writers. To test whether this clustering exceeded chance, we asked how many of the 11 bromodomain inhibitors present in the 278-drug panel fell among the mesothelioma top candidates. Bromodomain inhibitors were over-represented: 3 of the top 5 (hypergeometric $P = 4.5 \times 10^{-4}$) and 4 of the top 10 ($P = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$) survival-associated drugs were bromodomain inhibitors. This enrichment is restricted to the bromodomain class and must be interpreted in light of the strong inter-drug correlation among these compounds (mean off-diagonal Pearson $r = 0.78$ across the panel; $r = 0.987$ between the two BET inhibitors I-BET-762 and OTX015), which means the bromodomain hits are not statistically independent and the enrichment reflects a single correlated axis rather than 11 independent confirmations. With that caveat, the over-representation is consistent with the central role of BAP1 – a chromatin deubiquitinase and the most frequently mutated gene in mesothelioma – as a driver of this malignancy [16].

In **adrenocortical carcinoma**, the top candidates included Methotrexate (antifolate; log-rank $p = 8.2 \times 10^{-6}$; per-SD HR = 0.40, 95% CI 0.27-0.57), Axitinib (VEGFR inhibitor; $p = 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$; per-SD HR = 0.41, 95% CI 0.27-0.60), Vinorelbine (vinca alkaloid; $p = 1.8 \times 10^{-5}$), VX-11e (ERK inhibitor; $p = 4.2 \times 10^{-5}$), and Daporinad (NAMPT inhibitor; $p = 4.4 \times 10^{-5}$). Axitinib is FDA-approved for renal cell carcinoma [17], which lowers the barrier to experimental evaluation should the association be substantiated; we emphasise, however, that the present analysis nominates this pathway as a hypothesis and does not establish predictive efficacy in ACC.

In **uveal melanoma**, Serdemetan (MDM2 inhibitor; log-rank $p = 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$; per-SD HR = 0.48, 95% CI 0.32-0.69) and Tanespimycin (HSP90 inhibitor; $p = 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$; per-SD HR = 0.46, 95% CI 0.31-0.67) were the top candidates. The prominence of an MDM2 inhibitor is biologically coherent: unlike cutaneous melanoma, UVM is driven by GNAQ/GNA11 mutations and rarely harbours TP53 mutations, leaving the p53 pathway intact and therapeutically targetable through MDM2 inhibition [18]. We note, however, that the UVM associations were the least reproducible of the three cancers under repeated split-half resampling (see Statistical validation, below), and should be regarded as the most tentative of the nominated candidate sets.

Pathway enrichment reveals mechanistic themes

Because the input to each enrichment is that drug’s own IDWAS gene ranking, the pathways below characterise the gene-expression programme the model keys on to predict sensitivity rather than the tumour’s biology directly; they are most safely read as the learned signature underlying each nomination. GSEA of IDWAS gene rankings for the top survival-associated drug per cancer type revealed consistent pathway themes (Figure 4). In mesothelioma, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) was the most strongly enriched resistance pathway for Remodelin (NES = 3.32, FDR < 0.001), while oxidative phosphorylation was associated with sensitivity. This is consistent with the clinical distinction between epithelioid (better prognosis) and sarcomatoid (worse prognosis, more mesenchymal) mesothelioma subtypes [19].

In ACC, E2F targets (NES = -3.10) and G2-M checkpoint (NES = -2.99) drove Methotrexate sensitivity, consistent with the antifolate mechanism of action targeting rapidly proliferating cells. Bile acid metabolism was uniquely enriched as a resistance pathway (NES = 1.91), reflecting the adrenal cortex’s steroidogenic function.

Across cancer types, EMT was consistently associated with drug resistance, while E2F/MYC/cell-cycle signatures were associated with sensitivity. This recurrent axis should be interpreted cautiously: an EMT-high/proliferation-low transcriptional state is itself a well-established poor-prognosis signature across many carcinomas, largely independent of any specific drug. Its

appearance as the dominant pathway theme for the top drug in several cancers therefore raises the possibility that part of the survival association we detect reflects alignment between imputed sensitivity and a generic prognostic signature, rather than drug-specific pharmacology. The biological coherence of individual candidates (for example, MDM2 inhibition in p53-intact UVM) argues against this explaining the entire signal, but it cannot be excluded as a contributor, and it reinforces the prognostic-versus-predictive distinction developed in the Discussion.

SHAP biomarkers validate model biological accuracy

SHAP analysis of the most predictable drugs recovered biologically expected biomarkers (Figure 5). For AZD5991 (MCL1 inhibitor), the strongest resistance-associated gene was BCL2L1 (BCL-XL), the compensatory anti-apoptotic protein that mediates resistance to MCL1 inhibition [20]; the direction of this effect was read from the sign of the standardised ridge coefficient (Methods), and a supplementary table reporting effect direction from the near-zero mean signed SHAP value has been corrected accordingly (Supplementary Table S4). Recovery of this known pharmacogenomic relationship supports, but on its own does not establish, the biological fidelity of the transfer models; it is one positive control rather than a systematic validation across drugs.

For Remodelin in mesothelioma, the top SHAP genes included FMOD (fibromodulin), POSTN (periostin), and THBS2 (thrombospondin-2) – all extracellular matrix and mesenchymal marker genes. This mesenchymal gene signature aligns with the EMT pathway enrichment from GSEA, confirming the finding through an independent method. These SHAP genes do not overlap with the genes most strongly ranked in the IDWAS volcano for the same drug (FBN1, ITGA5, FN1; Supplementary Figure S3); the two methods rank genes by different quantities – model attribution versus marginal expression-sensitivity correlation – so non-overlap of the top-labelled genes is expected, and both sets are extracellular-matrix/mesenchymal, converging on the same EMT programme rather than the same individual genes.

Internal consistency: drug-drug clustering

Hierarchical clustering of drug-drug correlations in imputed sensitivity profiles confirmed that drugs with shared mechanisms of action clustered together. I-BET-762 and OTX015 (both BET bromodomain inhibitors) showed $r = 0.987$, while Camptothecin and Irinotecan (both topoisomerase I inhibitors) showed $r = 0.978$. This mechanistic coherence provides further evidence that the transfer learning models capture genuine pharmacological relationships rather than noise.

Statistical validation

Label-permutation testing was applied independently to the three cancers with non-zero nominal hits. In every case the observed number of FDR-significant drugs exceeded the permutation mean by a wide margin: mesothelioma (observed 39 vs permuted mean 1.1, SD 6.7; empirical $p = 0.02$; Figure 6A), adrenocortical carcinoma (59 vs 1.0, SD 8.3; $p = 0.02$), and uveal melanoma (16 vs 0.1, SD 1.1; $p = 0.01$). Two features of these nulls warrant emphasis. First, the permutation distributions are heavily right-skewed: occasional label permutations produced large false-positive blooms (maximum permuted counts of 55, 83, and 11 drugs for MESO, ACC, and UVM respectively), so that for ACC a small number of permutations exceeded even the observed count. This is the expected behaviour when Benjamini-Hochberg correction is applied across 278 strongly correlated tests, and it is the reason we treat the within-cancer FDR q-values as a ranking device and the permutation empirical p-value as the primary significance anchor. Second, despite this heavy tail, the aggregate signal in all three cancers fell at or beyond the 98th percentile of its null, indicating that the collection of associations as a whole is not a chance artefact.

Reproducibility was assessed by repeated split-half resampling (100 random partitions per cancer; Figure 6B shows the mesothelioma exemplar). The mean between-half correlation of $-\log_{10}(p\text{-values})$ decreased monotonically across the three cancers: adrenocortical carcinoma was the most

reproducible (mean $r = 0.24$, SD 0.13; positive in 95% of splits), mesothelioma was modestly reproducible (mean $r = 0.19$, SD 0.16; 88% positive), and uveal melanoma was the weakest (mean $r = 0.14$, SD 0.16; 78% positive). The single-split estimate is itself noisy — across the 100 partitions the mesothelioma correlation ranged widely — underscoring that split-half replication on cohorts of this size provides a directional indication of reproducibility rather than a precise statistic. Taken together, the permutation and resampling analyses support the aggregate survival signal as exceeding chance while placing the strongest confidence on the ACC associations, intermediate confidence on MESO, and the most tentative confidence on UVM.

Because the permutation test establishes only that the aggregate signal is real, we asked separately whether each headline association is drug-specific or merely a re-expression of the dominant correlated axis (Supplementary Table S6). The first principal component (PC1) of the within-cancer sensitivity matrix captured roughly half its variance (53%, 55%, and 47% in ACC, MESO, and UVM) and was itself significantly prognostic only in ACC (HR = 0.53, $p = 0.002$), being weak and non-significant in MESO (HR = 0.93, $p = 0.58$) and UVM (HR = 1.18, $p = 0.36$). Crucially, every headline drug’s hazard ratio persisted — indeed strengthened — after adjustment for PC1: ACC Methotrexate moved from HR = 0.40 ($p = 1 \times 10^{-6}$) to HR = 0.29 ($p = 1 \times 10^{-4}$), MESO Remodelin was essentially unchanged at HR = 1.71 ($p = 4 \times 10^{-5}$), and UVM Serdemetan moved from HR = 0.48 ($p = 1 \times 10^{-4}$) to HR = 0.34 ($p = 3 \times 10^{-6}$); in ACC, PC1 itself became non-significant once the drug was included ($p = 0.22$). A complementary drug-identity null placed each headline in the extreme tail of the 278-drug distribution: only 6 (2.2%), 3 (1.1%), and 5 (1.8%) of drugs reached an overall-survival association at least as strong as Methotrexate, Remodelin, and Serdemetan respectively. The headline associations are therefore not interchangeable members of an undifferentiated correlated cloud; they carry prognostic information beyond the dominant correlated axis. Because PC1 captured only about half of the matrix variance (47-55%), this conditioning removes the single dominant correlated direction but not residual structure in higher principal components; the associations are accordingly specific beyond that dominant axis rather than fully independent of all shared structure, and this within-cohort test cannot exclude residual confounding by unmeasured prognostic factors.

External validation in an independent pharmacogenomic dataset

To test whether the most prominent mechanistic theme — the over-representation of bromodomain and BET inhibitors among the mesothelioma survival-associated drugs (OF-1, CPI-637, RVX-208) — reflects a genuine target-class vulnerability of mesothelioma rather than an artefact of correlated imputed-sensitivity ranking, we sought corroboration in the Cancer Therapeutics Response Portal (CTRPv2), an independent small-molecule sensitivity screen of cancer cell lines that shares no compounds with our top mesothelioma list. CTRPv2 contains eleven mesothelioma cell lines and three single-agent BET inhibitors (JQ-1, I-BET151, and GSK525762A); because these molecules differ from the GDSC-derived candidates, agreement would constitute independent target-class support rather than a re-measurement of the same compounds.

Mesothelioma cell lines were not preferentially sensitive to BET inhibition. Across the three BET inhibitors, the median area under the dose-response curve (AUC; lower values denote greater sensitivity) in mesothelioma lines was indistinguishable from that of all other lineages (aggregate median AUC 0.84 versus 0.83; one-sided Mann-Whitney $p = 0.76$), placing mesothelioma at the 53rd percentile of cell-line sensitivity and tenth of twenty-one lineages with adequate sampling (Figure 7A). The null held for each compound individually (JQ-1 $p = 0.62$, I-BET151 $p = 0.84$, GSK525762A $p = 0.60$; Figure 7B). Critically, the same assay reproduced the canonical positive control: haematopoietic and lymphoid lines, the lineage with the best-established BET-inhibitor dependency, were markedly more sensitive than all other lineages (median AUC 0.71 versus 0.85; $p = 9 \times 10^{-51}$), confirming that the screen retained ample power to detect a true lineage-level vulnerability where one exists. The independent data therefore do not corroborate a mesothelioma-specific BET-class vulnerability; this negative result is consistent with the prognostic-versus-predictive concern raised

above — that the bromodomain enrichment in the imputed-sensitivity survival list may index a poor-prognosis transcriptional state rather than an actionable drug dependency — and it tempers, without contradicting, the preclinical reports of context-dependent BET activity in mesothelioma models that a fixed cell-line panel may not capture.

Discussion

This study nominates a prioritised set of candidate repurposing drugs across five rare cancers that collectively lack therapeutic options. The strongest signals (59 nominal associations in adrenocortical carcinoma, 39 in mesothelioma) point to mechanistically coherent candidate vulnerabilities: bromodomain-class over-representation in BAP1-driven mesothelioma, antiproliferative targeting in ACC, and p53-pathway reactivation in UVM. These patterns emerged from pharmacogenomic transfer learning (GDSC cell lines to TCGA tumours), with pathway enrichments and a positive-control biomarker (BCL2L1/MCL1) consistent with the models capturing genuine pharmacology — though, as the external cell-line check of the mesothelioma theme illustrates below, mechanistic coherence of a nominated class does not guarantee that it represents an actionable dependency.

What this analysis can and cannot establish

The interpretive frame for everything that follows is the distinction between a prognostic and a predictive signal. Our design stratifies patients by imputed sensitivity to a drug and asks whether that stratification tracks overall survival. A positive result demonstrates that the gene-expression programme the model uses to predict sensitivity to that drug is associated with prognosis in that cancer; it does not demonstrate that administering the drug would change outcome, which is a predictive claim that only an interventional comparison can support. This distinction is not a peripheral caveat but the governing limitation of the approach, and it is sharpened by two observations from our own data. First, the recurrent pathway theme across cancers — EMT-high resistance, proliferation-high sensitivity — coincides with a generic poor-prognosis transcriptional signature, so some of the survival association may reflect the imputed-sensitivity score acting as a surrogate prognostic marker rather than as a drug-specific predictor. Second, because the 278 imputed drug profiles are strongly correlated, many of the individual “FDR-significant” associations are not independent discoveries; the permutation test, which respects this correlation, supports the aggregate signal but does not license reading each per-drug q-value as a calibrated error rate. We therefore present the candidates below as biologically interpretable hypotheses for experimental testing, ordered by the strength of their internal-resampling support (ACC > MESO > UVM), and we are deliberately cautious about language implying clinical readiness.

Mesothelioma: a candidate epigenetic theme that did not externally replicate

The over-representation of bromodomain inhibitors (OF-1, CPI-637, RVX-208) among the top mesothelioma candidates aligns mechanistically with the central role of BAP1 loss in this disease: BAP1 encodes a chromatin deubiquitinase, and its inactivation leads to widespread epigenetic dysregulation [16]. Individual BET bromodomain inhibitors have shown context-dependent preclinical activity in particular mesothelioma models [21]. Our direct test of this theme, however, was negative: in the independent CTRPv2 cell-line screen, mesothelioma lines were not preferentially sensitive to BET inhibition as a class, even though the same screen recovered the canonical haematopoietic BET dependency (Results; Figure 7). The imputation-based survival associations are therefore best read as a prognostic pattern among strongly correlated compounds that is consistent with the BAP1 biology but is not corroborated by orthogonal cell-line pharmacology — a discrepancy that may reflect the difference between intrinsic cell-line sensitivity and a patient-level prognostic axis, or genuine absence of a class-level vulnerability, and that only direct experimental testing can resolve. The accompanying association of EMT with drug resistance is consistent with the epithelioid-to-sarcomatoid transition representing an axis of treatment failure in mesothelioma [19], while also

being the component of our signal most likely to overlap with a generic prognostic transcriptional state.

Remodelin, targeting NAT10, is a particularly interesting candidate. NAT10 acetylates both histones and RNA, and its inhibition has been shown to rescue nuclear morphology defects in laminopathic cells [22]. The relevance to mesothelioma – a cancer arising from mesothelial cells with frequent disruption of nuclear architecture genes – warrants further investigation.

For the Australian research community, these findings are relevant given the disproportionate mesothelioma burden in Australia due to historical asbestos exposure [10]. The nomination of epigenetic-class candidates through computational pharmacogenomics could, if substantiated pre-clinically, help prioritise targets for future investigation in the Australian mesothelioma patient population.

Adrenocortical carcinoma: actionable candidates

The identification of Axitinib (FDA-approved VEGFR inhibitor [17]) as a top ACC candidate (per-SD HR = 0.41, 95% CI 0.27-0.60) is of interest because an existing approval and safety record would lower the practical barrier to a confirmatory study, should the association be substantiated experimentally; the present result is a nomination, not evidence of efficacy in ACC. The ACC associations carried the strongest internal-resampling support of the three cancers, which is the basis for our relative confidence in this cohort. The enrichment of E2F/cell-cycle pathways in Methotrexate sensitivity is mechanistically sound, as antifolates preferentially target rapidly dividing cells, though it is also the pathway most aligned with the generic proliferation-prognosis axis noted above. The appearance of Daporinad (NAMPT inhibitor) among top candidates in both ACC and (nominally) THYM is consistent with shared metabolic features of these endocrine-related rare cancers, but THYM yielded no FDR-significant associations and this observation should be treated as exploratory.

Uveal melanoma: exploiting intact p53

The prominence of Serdemetan (MDM2 inhibitor) in UVM exploits a distinctive feature of this cancer: unlike cutaneous melanoma, UVM is driven by GNAQ/GNA11 mutations and rarely harbours TP53 mutations [18]. This intact p53 pathway creates a therapeutic window for MDM2 inhibitors that would not be available in TP53-mutant cancers. Tanespimycin (HSP90 inhibitor) may complement this by destabilising the constitutively active GNAQ/GNA11 oncoproteins that drive UVM.

From nominated hypotheses to experimental tests

The candidates identified here are starting points for experimental work, not protocols ready for the clinic, and the appropriate next steps are graded accordingly. The most immediate and lowest-cost validations are computational and preclinical rather than interventional: replication of the imputed-sensitivity-survival associations in independent pharmacogenomic resources and additional tumour expression cohorts beyond TCGA, followed by in vitro testing of the nominated compounds against patient-derived rare-cancer models. We took the first such step here, cross-checking the mesothelioma bromodomain theme against the CTRPv2 cell-line screen; mesothelioma lines showed no preferential BET-class sensitivity (Results), which is a cautionary signal that some of these nominations may not survive orthogonal testing. Only candidates that do survive these stages would reasonably warrant consideration for early-phase clinical evaluation. Within that ordering, the underlying biology of some candidates remains plausible — BET bromodomain inhibitors have documented context-dependent preclinical activity in mesothelioma models [21] that a fixed cell-line panel may not capture, and MDM2 inhibition is mechanistically matched to the near-universal retention of wild-type TP53 in uveal melanoma — and the existing approval of Axitinib would shorten the path for ACC if its association replicates; but the mesothelioma cell-line null cautions against treating

mechanistic plausibility as a substitute for direct experimental confirmation. We deliberately avoid proposing specific trial designs here: the convergence of several correlated bromodomain inhibitors in the mesothelioma list is better read as a single class-level hypothesis to be tested preclinically than as independent evidence justifying a basket or platform trial, and framing it otherwise would overstate what an imputation-based survival association can support.

Limitations

Several limitations should be noted; the most fundamental — that the design supports a prognostic rather than a predictive interpretation — is developed above as the governing frame for the Discussion and is not repeated here.

First, the transfer learning approach assumes that gene expression-drug sensitivity relationships observed in cell lines are preserved in patient tumours. While quantile normalisation mitigates distributional differences, cell lines lack the tumour microenvironment, immune infiltration, and stromal interactions present in vivo, which may modulate drug sensitivity. The cell-line and tumour expression matrices were also quantified in different units (TPM versus FPKM); per-gene quantile normalisation absorbs most of this discrepancy but cannot guarantee removal of residual cross-platform bias. We performed one external check against an independent cell-line drug-screening dataset (CTRPv2), and it did not corroborate the most prominent mechanistic theme: mesothelioma cell lines were not preferentially sensitive to BET inhibition, despite the same assay recovering the canonical BET dependency of haematopoietic lines (Results; Figure 7). This negative result must itself be interpreted cautiously — CTRPv2 measures intrinsic cell-line sensitivity rather than the patient-level survival endpoint our associations were built on, only eight mesothelioma lines carried BET-inhibitor data, and the independent compounds tested (JQ-1, I-BET151, GSK525762A) differ from the GDSC candidates — but it is a concrete instance of an imputed-sensitivity signal failing to replicate in orthogonal data, and it sets the agenda for the broader external replication (additional tumour-expression cohorts beyond TCGA and in vitro testing in patient-derived models) that remains the priority for follow-up.

Second, the GDSC compound set was screened across more than one assay wave, and the panel accordingly contains drugs with bimodal or batch-associated response distributions; we did not explicitly model screening-wave as a covariate, and residual batch structure could contribute to some imputed-sensitivity patterns.

Third, sample sizes for some rare cancers (particularly CHOL, $n = 33$, and the event-sparse THYM cohort with only 9 deaths) are small, limiting statistical power; the median-split hazard ratios from the unstandardised covariate were prone to near-complete-separation artefacts, which is why all reported hazard ratios are per-standard-deviation and Firth-penalised, and why no hazard ratio is reported for CHOL or THYM.

Fourth, the 278 imputed drug-sensitivity profiles are strongly correlated (mean pairwise $r = 0.78$), so the within-cancer Benjamini-Hochberg q -values do not provide strict family-wise error control across drugs; the headline count of 114 associations should be read as a ranking rather than as 114 independent discoveries, and the label-permutation test (which preserves the correlation structure) is the appropriate significance anchor. The same correlation means the bromodomain-class enrichment reflects one correlated axis rather than independent confirmations. To check that the headline associations are not simply a re-expression of this dominant correlated axis, each was conditioned on the first principal component of the within-cancer sensitivity matrix; all three survived adjustment and sat in the top ~ 1 – 2% of drugs by survival association (Results; Supplementary Table S6). Because PC1 captures only about half the matrix variance, this conditions out the single dominant correlated direction but not residual structure in higher principal components, so the claim is specificity beyond that dominant axis rather than full independence from all shared prognostic structure, and it cannot exclude residual confounding by unmeasured prognostic factors. Relatedly, the orthogonal cell-line check we applied to the mesothelioma theme cannot be extended to the

ACC headline — the strongest of our three signals — because adrenocortical carcinoma is essentially absent from the CTRPv2/CCLC cell-line panels (no adrenocortical lineage is represented), leaving the ACC nominations without an independent pharmacogenomic cross-check.

Fifth, the high proportion of predictable drugs (97% at $R^2 > 0.1$) reflects the permissive threshold used to maximise drug coverage; at $R^2 > 0.3$ only 60% of drugs remain predictable, so a substantial fraction of the panel is imputed with modest accuracy.

Sixth, the IDWAS analysis correlates gene expression with imputed drug sensitivity, which is itself a function of gene expression via the ridge model – creating partial circularity. The SHAP analysis provides a more direct decomposition and should be preferred for biomarker interpretation.

Finally, ridge regression captures only linear gene-drug relationships and may miss non-linear interactions that methods such as XGBoost or neural networks could detect, and the variance filtering threshold of 5,000 genes was chosen for computational convenience without formal evaluation of its effect on results.

Conclusions

Pharmacogenomic transfer learning from cell lines to tumours can systematically generate mechanistically interpretable drug-repurposing hypotheses for rare cancers that are otherwise under-served by drug development. Applied to five TCGA rare cancers, the approach nominated pathway-concordant candidate classes — bromodomain and other epigenetic inhibitors in BAP1-driven mesothelioma, antiproliferative agents in ACC, and MDM2 inhibition exploiting intact p53 in UVM — with internal-resampling support that was strongest in ACC, intermediate in mesothelioma, and weakest in UVM. These are prioritised hypotheses rather than clinically validated treatments: the survival associations are prognostic in nature and partly entangled with a generic poor-prognosis transcriptional signature, and the candidate classes are internally correlated. An external check of the leading mesothelioma theme is illustrative — bromodomain inhibitors showed no preferential activity against mesothelioma cell lines in an independent screen — underscoring that mechanistic plausibility does not guarantee replication. The appropriate next steps are broader external pharmacogenomic replication and preclinical testing in patient-derived rare-cancer models, which would determine whether any of these nominations merits clinical investigation. The mesothelioma candidates are of particular interest in the Australian context given the country’s disproportionate asbestos-related disease burden.

Declarations

Ethics statement

No ethics approval was required for this study. All data used are publicly available through open-access portals (GDSC, DepMap, TCGA/GDC) and contain no individually identifiable patient information.

Author contributions

HF conceived the study, designed the methodology, performed all analyses, and wrote the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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AI tool disclosure

Computational code development was assisted by Claude (Anthropic). All analytical decisions, biological interpretations, and manuscript content were determined by the author. The analysis pipeline code is available for full transparency.

Data availability

All data used in this study are publicly available. GDSC drug sensitivity data were obtained from cancerrxgene.org (release 8.5). Cell line gene expression data were obtained from the DepMap portal (release 24Q4). TCGA data were accessed through the GDC API (portal.gdc.cancer.gov). The complete analysis pipeline is available as a self-contained Jupyter notebook at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19535800>.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. Ridge regression model performance. (A) Distribution of 5-fold cross-validation R^2 across 286 GDSC drugs; dashed line indicates the $R^2 = 0.1$ predictability threshold. (B) $CV R^2$ as a function of the number of cell lines with IC_{50} data per drug.

Figure 2. Heatmap of mean imputed drug sensitivity across five rare cancer types for the 30 most variable drugs. Blue indicates predicted sensitivity (lower IC_{50}), red indicates resistance.

Figure 3. Kaplan-Meier survival curves for the top four survival-associated drugs in mesothelioma. Patients were stratified by median imputed drug sensitivity into sensitive and resistant groups. Log-rank p-values are shown.

Figure 4. GSEA pathway enrichment for the top survival-associated drug in each of the three cancers with FDR-significant associations: ACC (Methotrexate), MESO (Remodelin), and UVM (Serdemetan). Bar plots show normalised enrichment scores (NES) for MSigDB Hallmark pathways. Red bars indicate pathways enriched in resistance (positive NES), blue bars indicate pathways enriched in sensitivity (negative NES). CHOL and THYM are omitted as no drug reached FDR significance in those cancers.

Figure 5. SHAP biomarker analysis for the two most predictable drugs. Mean absolute SHAP values for the top 15 genes driving sensitivity predictions for AZD5991 (MCL1 inhibitor) and Schweinfurthin A. Red indicates resistance-associated genes and blue indicates sensitivity-associated genes, with the direction of each gene’s effect taken from the sign of its standardised ridge coefficient (Methods; Supplementary Table S4).

Figure 6. Statistical validation (mesothelioma exemplar; per-cancer statistics for ACC and UVM are reported in the text). (A) Label-permutation histogram showing the number of FDR-significant drugs from 100 permutations (grey; mean 1.1, heavy right tail with maximum 55) versus the real data (red dashed line; 39 drugs), empirical $p = 0.02$. (B) Distribution of between-half correlations of $-\log_{10}(\log\text{-rank } p\text{-values})$ across 100 random split-half partitions of the mesothelioma cohort; the red dashed line marks the mean ($r = 0.19$), and correlations were positive in 88% of partitions, illustrating modest but directionally consistent reproducibility on a cohort of this size.

Figure 7. External validation against an independent pharmacogenomic dataset (CTRPv2). (A) BET-class sensitivity by lineage: per-cell-line mean area under the dose-response curve (AUC; lower = more sensitive) across the three single-agent BET inhibitors in CTRPv2, summarised by lineage (boxplots; lineages with at least eight cell lines shown), ordered by median sensitivity. Mesothelioma (pleura; crimson) sits mid-distribution at the tenth of twenty-one lineages, whereas haematopoietic/lymphoid lines (green; positive control) are the most sensitive. The dotted line marks the panel-wide median. (B) Per-compound view for JQ-1, I-BET151, and GSK525762A: grey violins show the full cell-line AUC distribution, crimson points the mesothelioma lines, and black bars the panel median; mesothelioma lines scatter through the middle of each distribution rather than at the sensitive extreme.